

**Review report on extended abstract titled
“Open Data and Researcher Assessment in the Social Sciences and
Humanities (SSH): Addressing Challenges and Building Tailored
Support”**

Authors (alphabetically by last name)

Silvio Peroni^a (0000-0003-0530-4305), Thanasis Vergoulis^b (0000-0003-0555-4128)

^aUniversity of Bologna, Italy; ^bATHENA RC, Greece

Feedback Reviewer 1 Silvio Peroni

	Reviewer 1				
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID3	5	4	3	4	Accept

The poster abstract provides a clear description of the issues in measuring and pushing researchers to adopt Open Science practices and how these have been addressed in the context of the University of Oulu in Finland. In particular, the abstract clarifies how the University has implemented a discipline-specific approach to work with researchers (in particular in the SSH domain) to publish their data in appropriate trusted repositories - and, by means of this, to implement harvesting strategies to store the bibliographic metadata of the data published in the University research information system, i.e. OuluCRIS.

The poster aligns well with the conference topics and offers a concrete illustration of the applications of some Open Science principles, as evidenced by the increasing number of open data records published annually at the University of Oulu. As a minor concern, it is not entirely clear what those practices are that were introduced and implemented at the University, but I am sure they will be introduced properly during the poster presentation, being a central part of this abstract.

Feedback Reviewer 2 Thanasis Vergoulis

	Reviewer 2				
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID3	5	4	2	3	Borderline

The extended abstract outlines a poster highlighting the University of Oulu's efforts to support Open Science among SSH researchers in Finland, with a focus on the challenges faced for credit and recognition of Open Science practices in the domain. The topic is relevant to the conference, and the initiatives described are valuable. While the abstract does not present novel ideas (nor are any expected in the poster) this is probably acceptable within the scope of a conference poster session. However, the abstract is prone to various language issues (e.g., inconsistencies using US spelling in some cases, while UK spelling is mainly used by the abstract) and typos (e.g., missing "the" in front of "IT Center for Science"). Moreover, in some cases, the clarity of the sentences would benefit from some restructuring. As a result, the abstract should be revised to address such issues and ideally reviewed by a native English speaker before publication.